

**CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF THE WORK COMPLETED ON THE
DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF
FUTURE POWER ENGINEERS**

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Abstract

This article highlights the importance of training highly qualified energy engineers with professional competencies in the context of globalization and technological progress. It explores the concept of "competence," examines its theoretical and practical aspects, and analyzes scientific interpretations by national and international scholars. It substantiates the need to develop theoretical knowledge, practical skills, creativity, critical thinking, and digital technology proficiency in energy engineers. Furthermore, it analyzes PhD and DSc dissertations in pedagogical sciences defended in the republic from 2003 to 2025, revealing the quantity and content of scientific research in the field of teaching and education theory and methodology based on statistical indicators.

Keywords

energy engineers, competence, competency-based approach, energy education, theoretical knowledge, practical skills, creative thinking, digital technologies, innovative methods.

Introduction. In the modern era of rapid technological development, high rates of industrial growth, and innovative transformations in the energy sector, training qualified engineering personnel is becoming a critical task. Under these conditions, there

is a growing need for specialists with modern knowledge and skills not only in production but also in research, design, engineering, and management.

Future engineers bear a high level of professional responsibility, so their training should not be limited to technical and scientific disciplines. It is essential to develop communication skills, the ability to effectively use information technology, critical thinking, creativity, and teamwork skills. For students majoring in energy, these skills are especially important for ensuring the continuity and safety of production processes, as well as for teaching energy efficiency improvements.

Today, engineering education in the energy sector faces a number of complex challenges, including the insufficient alignment of training content with production needs. In this regard, there is a growing need to establish effective cooperation between universities and industrial enterprises based on dual training, optimization of curricula taking into account real technological requirements, and the organization of practical and laboratory classes in modern, well-equipped laboratories.

Research on the teaching content of energy disciplines within the specialty "Theory and Methods of Teaching and Education (Engineering)" was conducted by young scientists of the republic L.A. Nematov, A.N. Mamatkulov, Sh.A. Pazilova, U.A. Eshniyozov, and D.Kh. Khalmanov and yielded positive results.

Teaching methods for individual technical disciplines were developed by Russian researchers D.A. Eshnazarov, Ya.A. Suyunova, M.Dzh. Gofirov, U.Dzh. Khasanov, S.B. Atazhonova, O.S. Nurova, A.A. Parmanov, B.T. Karimov, Kh.M. Kurbanov, N.K. Abdullaev, U.B. Abdiev.

The following authors devoted their works to improving the teaching methods of specific areas of technical education: Zh.F. Madaminov, B.Y. Begmatov, U.A. Pardaboev, O.O. Nazarov, I.N. Saidaliev, Y.R. Zhuraev, Kh.I. Khanbabaev, D.I.

Kulmuradov, Sh.E. Karshiboev, O.S. Sultanov, M.K. Turakulova, O.Ch. Kuziev, I.I. Umirov, Sh.S. Khoshimova.

Russian scientists O.U. Eshmanov, R.K. Khudoykulov, K.A. Yadgarov, D.P. Mirzoev, U.A. Eshkuvvatov, D.D. Baratov, A.K. Bizhanov, N.M. Kuziev, V.E. Ubaidova, M.O. Holdorova, U.A. Nurullaev, A.Kh. Tillaev, M.A. Alimov.

According to foreign researchers D.E. Ryabova and A.V. Khutorskoy, competence is defined as an individual's readiness for action, that is, as a level of practical readiness based on knowledge, abilities, skills, personal qualities, values, and experience.

Analysis of the aforementioned scientific studies shows that the rapid development of science, engineering, and modern technology requires the training of students at technical universities in energy fields as specialists possessing a wide range of professional competencies that meet modern requirements. This, in turn, requires mastering the effective use of educational software in preparation for innovative activities.

In the training of future teachers of professional disciplines, the use of information, communication, and computer technologies as a didactic tool is of particular importance, serving as an important factor in improving the quality of education. However, an analysis of existing experience reveals a number of problems:

- Insufficient practice in using modern educational software in teaching specialized disciplines in the field of "Electric Power Engineering";
- Inadequacy of the teaching staff's capacity and the material and technical resources to meet innovative requirements;
- Insufficient software for organizing practical and laboratory classes in a virtual environment, as well as a lack of methodological materials for their use.

In the age of information exchange, a significant portion of human activity is associated with the collection, storage, analysis, and transmission of data. Therefore, preparing future engineers for work in a modern information environment plays a special role in developing their professional competencies. Information management skills are important not only for innovative educational activities but also in scientific research processes.

An engineer prepared for innovative work must be able to create innovations in their field, find scientifically sound solutions to existing problems, and search for and implement new information in practice. Performing such tasks requires the effective management and processing of large volumes of data. In this regard, automated educational information systems, knowledge bases, and data warehouses create important didactic opportunities. In recent years, special attention has been paid to this area in the country. However, despite this, the theoretical, practical, and scientific-methodological foundations for training future energy engineers as teachers of specialized disciplines for innovative work remain insufficiently developed. Although educational software is being widely implemented, their effective integration into the educational process requires a comprehensive approach.

In this study, abstracts of dissertations downloaded from the educational platform ziyonet.uz, completed between 2003 and 2025 in pedagogical sciences for the degrees of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) and Doctor of Science (DSc), were systematically analyzed to determine the number of defended dissertations and analyze their content. The total number of dissertations was found to be 2,054, of which 1,860 were for the PhD degree and 194 for the DSc degree. In the specialty 13.00.02 "Theory and Methods of Teaching and Education (by field)," the total number of dissertations was 692, of which 620 were for the PhD degree and 72 for the DSc degree (see Table 1).

Table 1

Number of dissertations defended in 2003–2025 in pedagogical sciences (PhD and DSc) and in the specialty 13.00.02 "Theory and Methods of Teaching and Education (by field)"

The total number of dissertations in pedagogical sciences for the degrees of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) and Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), completed in 2003–2025.		The total number of dissertations in pedagogical sciences for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) and Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), as well as dissertations in the specialty 13.00.02 - "Theory and methods of teaching and education (by field)", completed in 2003–2025.	
2054		692	
Of these, the total number of dissertations for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in pedagogical sciences.	Of these, the total number of dissertations is for the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc).	Of these, the total number of dissertations for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in pedagogical sciences in the specialty 13.00.02 - "Theory and	Of these, the total number of dissertations is for the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc) in the specialty 13.00.02 - "Theory and Methods of

		methods of teaching and education (by industry)".	Teaching and Education (by branch)".
1860	194	620	72

In the period 2003–2025, the total number of dissertations in the specialty 13.00.02 – “Theory and Methods of Teaching and Education (Engineering)” was forty-four (44), of which forty-one (41) were dissertations for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences, and three (3) were dissertations for the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc). This confirms the relevance of the chosen topic: among the studies devoted to teaching methods, the total number of dissertations aimed at improving the methodology for developing the professional competencies of future power engineers is eight (8), and all of them relate to dissertations for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences; dissertations for the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc) were not completed on this topic (see Table 2).

Table 2

Total number of dissertations for the degrees of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) and Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), completed in 2003–2025 in the specialty 13.00.02 – "Theory and Methods of Teaching and Education (Engineering)", as well as dissertations devoted to improving the methodology for developing the professional competencies of future power engineers.

<p>The total number of dissertations for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) and Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), completed in 2003–2025 in the specialty 13.00.02 – “Theory and Methods of Teaching and Education (Engineering)”.</p>		<p>The total number of dissertations for the degrees of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) and Doctor of Education (DSc), completed in 2003–2025 and dedicated to improving the methodology for developing the professional competencies of future power engineers.</p>	
44		8	
<p>Of these, the total number of dissertations is for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in pedagogical sciences in the specialty 13.00.02 - “Theory and methods of teaching and education (technology)”.</p>	<p>Of these, the total number of dissertations is for the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc) in the specialty 13.00.02 - “Theory and methods of teaching and education (technology)”.</p>	<p>Of these, the total number of dissertations for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in pedagogical sciences are devoted to improving the methodology for developing the professional competencies of future power engineers.</p>	<p>Of these, the total number of dissertations for the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc) are devoted to improving the methodology for developing the professional competencies of future power engineers.</p>
41	3	8	0

Conclusion: An analysis of dissertation research completed in the Republic from 2003 to 2025 revealed that virtually no research and teaching efforts were conducted to improve the methodology for developing the professional competencies of future energy engineers. This served as the methodological basis for selecting the topic of this dissertation—"Improving the Methodology for Developing the Professional Competencies of Future Energy Engineers"—and defining its specialty as 13.00.02 "Theory and Methodology of Teaching and Education (Engineering)" in preparation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences.

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